

Step-by-step guide to converting your DMP to the new template

Purpose of this guide

Data management plans (DMPs) of **research projects funded by Flemish public funds starting from September 2025** have to follow the new Flemish DMP template. This guide lists all changes between the original DMP template and the revised one. Although it is **not required to convert old DMPs** to the new template, this guide may be a useful tool for updating existing “DMP models” that were tailored to the needs of specific research groups.

Practical information

- This is a guide for switching a DMP from the first version of the Flemish DMP template (2022) to the second version (2025). Both versions of the template are published on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17025558>
- Creation date of this guide: August 2025
- Authors of this guide: members of the FRDN Project Group DMP (2023-2025)
- The DMP glossary is also updated to accommodate the new version of the DMP template. This glossary is published on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16918375>.

Step-by-step guide

The best way to convert a DMP is to start from the new DMP template – so that the questions and accompanying guidance are up to date – and copy-paste the answers from the original model. Note that all questions have been numbered in the new version.

Questions or items that are significantly changed and may need revision are listed in the table below. If a question or item is not listed, this means that it has not been altered (significantly).

Version information	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• A table for versioning information is added. This table can be used to keep track of the different versions of the DMP.
Data table (1.1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The digital vs. physical column has been removed.• The data types have been changed. The contents in this column should be reviewed (not copy-pasted).
Reused data (1.2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• A multiple choice menu has been added.
Ethical considerations (1.3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The original multiple choice menu has been expanded.• The category “human subjects” has been divided into “human participants” vs. “human bodily material”

	or patient data”.
Personal data (1.4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The original multiple choice menu has been expanded. • An explicit distinction has been made between collecting and processing personal data (new) vs. processing existing personal data (reuse).
Other ethical and legal considerations (1.5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The final 3 ethical and legal questions of the original template have been combined into 1 multiple choice menu.
Metadata (2.2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A multiple choice menu has been added.
Back-up (3.2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A multiple choice menu has been added.
Data preservation (4.1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A table has been added in which all datasets from the data table (1.1) should be listed. • The first 2 questions of the preservation section have been moved into this table. They should be answered for each dataset (or cluster of datasets). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tip: it is OK to write “min. 5 years” as an expected preservation period if the retention period is uncertain.
Data sharing (5.1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A table has been added in which all datasets from the first data table (1.1) should be listed. • The first 4 questions of the sharing section have been moved into this table. They should be answered for each dataset (or cluster of datasets). • The access levels have been expanded. It is possible to choose between open, embargoed, restricted, metadata only or closed.
Data usage license (5.3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A multiple choice menu has been added.
Persistent identifier (5.4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The original multiple choice menu (yes/no) has been removed. • This question can only be answered after publication of one or more datasets in a repository, as it is now required to fill in the persistent identifier(s) of the deposited dataset(s).
Responsibilities (6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This section is no longer divided according to the different phases of data management, but according to the status of the research project (during vs. after). • Explicit details are asked about the designated people (name and position). • The final question (6.3) has not changed.